

Bergmeister Papilla : A rare Anomaly of Papilla

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Article Info :

Received : 04/04/2024

Revised : 11/04/2024

Accepted: 23/04/2024

Available online: 23/04/2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11046389

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Clinical Image

Bergmeister papilla is a rare but benign congenital anomaly of the papilla. It's defined by the persistence of a peripapillary fibroglial tissue.

We report a case of a 50 years old man who came for an ophthalmological routine exam. Visual acuity was 20/20 for both eyes.

Anterior segment examination was unremarkable. The fundus exam of the right eye showed white fibrous tissue on the papilla. An optical coherence tomography was performed showing hyperreflective opacity on the optic nerve head.

Bergmeister papilla is characterised by avascular epipapillary membranes (remains of hyaloid artery) surrounding the head of the optic nerve head. It is as result of an anomaly of the development of the neuroectoderm tissue. Its prevalence among adults is 0.03%, however a pediatric study had shown a higher prevalence among premature infants. Generally found incidentally in a routine fundus exam, it is frequently asymptomatic. It is a benign condition although some cases of literature report complications such vitreous hemorrhage or retinal detachment due to contraction of the fibrovascular tissue.

Figure 1: Fundus photo demonstrating a Bergmeister papilla